

Emerging Automobile Innovations to be included in Motor Vehicle Mechanic Work Curriculum in Government Craft Development Center in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study assessed the emerging automobile innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State. Specifically, the study investigated maintenance, design and product innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State. Three (3) research questions were posed and answered and also three (3) hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. The study adopted Research and Development (R&D) design. The population of the study comprised of forty-three (43) respondents (8 MVMW Teachers and 35 Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians) in Rivers State. The entire population was studied due to its' manageable size. A questionnaire titled "Emerging Automobile Innovation Questionnaire (EAIQ)" was developed which comprised 30-items was used to elicit responses. The questionnaire was designed on a five (5) point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1) respectively. The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity by three (3) experts in the field of technical education. A reliability coefficient of .75 was determined on the instrument using Cronbach Alpha after a test-retest for an interval of ten (10) working days. Data collected for the study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and an inferential statistic of t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. It was decided to accept the null hypotheses if the significant level (Sig level) exceeds the probability level of .05, otherwise reject the null hypotheses. SPSS version 22 was used to aid the computation. The study recommended the Inclusion of maintenance, design and product innovations in the curriculum of motor vehicle mechanic works in government craft centers in Rivers State.

Keywords: Craft Center, Automobile Innovation and MVMW

INTRODUCTION

Craft development centers were established in response 'to the immediate need of craftsmen and artisans of which the state could only provide 7.5 percent of its needs. The craft development centers were industry-oriented to produce masons, plumbers, fitters, electricians, motor mechanics, etc. In course of 6 to 24 months' duration, opportunities were to be made available in the craft development centers for gifted and talented students to be developed for direct entry into appropriate classes in the junior and senior technical colleges to study in various trade such as pipe fitting and plumbing, block laying and concreting, mechanical engineering craft practice, electrical installation and maintenance works, motor vehicle mechanic works amongst others.

Motor vehicle mechanic work is a technical education programme that consist of the following tasks; maintenance, adjustment, inspecting, installing and repairs of automobile engines, engines accessories and power transmission (Ziblim, et. al., 2018). Motor Vehicle Mechanic trade as one of the mechanical trades in technical colleges is subdivided into Auto electric works, Vehicle body building, Agricultural Implement mechanics as well as motor vehicle mechanic works (NBTE, 2011). Ede and Olaitan (2010) asserted that the introduction of motor vehicle mechanic work (MVMW) and other trades in technical colleges are geared towards imparting basic knowledge as well as training skills that will leads to skilled graduates that would improve manpower, self-employed and competent workforce to meet the demands in the world of work. These components as stated by the NBTE (2011) are service station mechanic, petrol engine mechanics, steering and brake system Mechanics and Diesel Engine Maintenance Mechanics. Motor vehicle is a self-propelled land vehicle typically contains four wheels and an internal combustion engine, used for private or public transportation. This vehicle is of diverse types base on it styles, number of doors and purpose of uses. They are of different brands and models (maintenance, design and product) depending on the company or country that manufactured it, and are used for either public or convenience for private use (Bhandari, 2011).

Innovation is used to describe new or improved products, services, processes or practices that differ significantly from previous experiences. According to the Oslo Manual (Oslo Manual—Guidelines Proposal for Data Collection and Interpretation on Technological Innovation, which aims to guide and standardize concepts, methodologies and construction of R & D research statistics and indicators of industrialized countries, published in 1990 by the Organization for Modern technologies are distributed through mobile devices, dedicated networks, and specialized computers. Craftsmen require extensive skills and sufficient digital knowledge to exploit these technologies. They should understand how to program these devices, record, submit and retrieve data from the systems, and ways to connect different digital tools in the facility. Cooperation and Economic Development (OECD), is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product, good or service, or a process, or a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, in local organizations' work or external relations (OECD, 2005). With the development of science and technology, the automobile industry has undergone tremendous changes in innovation and technology applications. New types of mobile manned vehicles such as electric vehicles have changed human driving habits and mobile demands (Zeng, 2021). Innovation can take several forms: in products, production processes or management systems (Olumuyiwa, et al., 2014).

Maintenance innovation is a repair activity carried out on vehicles or other machines to keep them unaltered, and if altered, to restore them to their original state. For effective maintenance, Okwelle, Beako and Ajie (2017) further stated that expert opinion of mechanical technical skills obtained through organized vocational skills at the mechanical workshops and other skill acquisition centers that will improve entrepreneurship in the economy is essential and demanding. According to Usman (2007) maintenance implies taking specific steps and precautions to care for an automobile to ensure that it reaches its maximum life span. The life span of a vehicle will be shortened if emerging technical skills are not adopted in maintaining its components especially the transmission system for effective service delivery. Modern technologies are vital for optimizing maintenance work by simplifying and automating routine activities. The possibilities of these technologies are endless, and companies are continuously customizing them depending on their maintenance needs, available budgets, and the competencies of maintenance personnel

Design deals with the meanings that people give to products, and also with the product languages that one can devise to convey that meaning (Verganti, 2008). According to Krippendorff as cited in Verganti, (2008) "design is making sense (of things)". Designers give meaning to products by using a specific design language, which refers to the set of signs, symbols and icons to convey the message (Verganti, 2008) and to match socio-cultural models of the user (Dell'Era & Verganti, 2007). In the design of products, companies are manipulating the material parts of their products with the hope that customers will decode the meaning carried by those products; these particular actions have been referred to as the "*meaning-making actions*"

Product innovation will create various product designs, thereby increasing alternative choices, increasing the benefits or value received by customers, which in turn will improve product quality as expected by customers (Prajogo & Sohal, 2003). Companies can make various innovations by making various kinds of product designs, and adding value to an item, besides that the company can also innovate in the fields of 1) product innovation such as goods, services, ideas and places. 2) management innovations such as in work processes, production processes, marketing finance, etc. Innovation is very important for a company. Product innovation is also one of the impacts of rapid technological change. Rapid technological advances and high levels of competition require every company to continuously innovate products which will ultimately increase the company's competitive advantage. The company creates product innovations with a variety of product designs, thereby increasing alternative choices, increasing the benefits or value received by customers, so that product innovation is one way for companies to maintain competitive advantage.

Statement of Problem

The expectation of the society and the graduates is that of gaining employment in automotive industries, establishing a repair/ maintenance shop or going for further studies after graduation. However, the recent appearance of new car technologies signifies that there is currently a scarcity of experts familiar with the unique design and characteristics of these vehicles because most mechanics and workers employed in garages and repair shops generally have an elementary school education or have never finished high school. This lack of skilled personnel is a problem for the manufacturing and maintenance of these vehicles (Lopez-Arquillos, 2015). Furthermore, the researchers also observed that graduates of motor vehicle and maintenance work lack practical skills to work on or maintain recently produce vehicles to the expectations and satisfaction of their employers. This is not far from the fact that the skills acquired in craft centers no longer match the demands of the market and industry, thereby causing a gap between what is currently required in the industry and the skills acquired by motor vehicle and maintenance work graduates of craft centers. Thus, the authors having critically observed this lapses in the curriculum of motor vehicle and maintenance work decide to carry out the present study on emerging

automobile innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

Aim/Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to assess the emerging automobile innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to assess the:

1. Maintenance innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State
2. Design innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State
3. Product innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State

Research Questions

The following three (3) research questions guided the study.

1. What maintenance innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State?
2. What design innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State?
3. What product innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

Three (3) hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

H01: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on maintenance innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on design innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State

H03: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on product innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the Research and Development (R & D) design. according to Borg and Gall (2007) research and development (R & D) is used when research findings is utilized in designing and developing new programmes, materials, that will provide knowledge and skills, research and development is appropriate. The population of the study comprised of forty-three (43) respondents (8 MVMW Teachers and 35 Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians) in Rivers State. The entire population of respondents was studied; hence the study was a census. A questionnaire titled “Emerging Automobile Innovation Questionnaire (EAIQ)” was develop which comprised 30-items was used to elicit responses. The questionnaire was designed on a five (5) point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1) respectively.

The instrument for the study validated by three (3) experts; two (2) drawn from Department of Technical Education (Automobile Technology Option), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt, and One from the Department of Automobile Technology, Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka – Lagos. A reliability coefficient of .75 was determined on the instrument using Cronbach Alpha after a test-retest for an interval of ten (10) working days. Data collected for the study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation and an inferential statistic of t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. It was decided to accept the null hypotheses if the significant level (Sig level) exceeds the probability level of .05, otherwise reject the null hypotheses.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What maintenance innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Responses of MVMW Teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on Maintenance Innovations to be included in MVMW Curriculum of Craft Development Center

S/N	Items	MVMW Teachers N = 8			Registered MVM Technicians N = 35		
		\bar{x}	SD	RMK	\bar{x}	SD	RMK
1.	Condition-monitoring sensors	3.64	.886	Agree	3.75	.933	Agree
2.	Onboard diagnostics II (OBD II)	3.84	.770	Agree	3.62	.869	Agree
3.	Dual-clutch transmission	3.84	.857	Agree	3.79	.936	Agree
4.	Turbocharger	3.89	.748		4.00	.823	Agree
5.	Start/Stop Technology	3.74	.816	Agree	3.59	.835	Agree
6.	Engine speed sensor Intake	3.92	.839	Agree	4.03	.718	Agree
7.	Air-temperature sensor	3.90	.838	Agree	3.70	.854	Agree
8.	Computerized Maintenance Management Systems (CMMS)	3.58	.860	Agree	3.65	1.065	Agree
9.	Big Data & Analytics	3.67	.941	Agree	3.44	1.059	Agree
10.	Cloud technology	3.70	.875	Agree	3.67	1.016	Agree
Grand Mean		3.772	.843	Agree	3.724	.910	Agree

Source: Authors (2023)

Data in Table 1 revealed that MVMW Teachers had a grand mean of 3.772 and the standard deviation range of .843. While the registered MVM Technicians had a grand mean of 3.724 and its standard deviation was .910. This indicates that the respondents agreed that maintenance innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents.

Research Question 2: What design innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Responses of MVMW Teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on Design Innovations to be included in MVMW Curriculum of Craft Development Center

S/N	Items	MVMW Teachers N = 8			Registered MVM Technicians N = 35		
		\bar{x}	SD	RMK	\bar{x}	SD	RMK
1.	Artificial Intelligence	3.95	1.038	Agree	3.51	.917	Agree
2.	Human-Machine Interfaces	3.71	.958	Agree	3.72	.971	Agree
3.	Internet of Things	3.65	1.065	Agree	3.56	1.027	Agree
4.	Autonomous Vehicles	3.89	.721	Agree	3.86	.924	Agree
5.	Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS)	3.75	1.047	Agree	3.72	.931	Agree
6.	Electrification	3.70	1.026	Agree	3.77	.896	Agree
7.	Additive manufacturing (3D Printing)	3.62	.941	Agree	3.38	1.051	Agree
8.	Blockchain	3.31	.968	Agree	3.66	1.063	Agree
9.	Security/Guiding Intelligence	3.81	.840	Agree	3.51	1.014	Agree
10.	Driverless Cars	3.76	.837	Agree	3.77	.998	Agree
Grand Mean		3.715	.844	Agree	3.646	.979	Agree

Data in Table 2 revealed that MVMW Teachers had a grand mean of 3.715 and the standard deviation range of .844. While the registered MVM Technicians had a grand mean of 3.646 and its standard deviation was .979. This

indicates that the respondents agreed that the design innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents.

Research Question 3: What product innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Responses of MVMW Teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on Product Innovations to be included in MVMW Curriculum of Craft Development Center

S/N	Items	MVMW Teachers			Registered MVM Technicians		
		\bar{x}	SD	RMK	\bar{x}	SD	RMK
1.	Adaptive cruise control	3.69	.949	Agree	3.54	.930	Agree
2.	Auto security systems with push-button remotes	3.84	.816	Agree	3.76	.777	Agree
3.	Front-engine, front-drive	3.86	.843	Agree	3.87	.751	Agree
4.	Crumple zones	3.81	.871	Agree	3.75	1.062	Agree
5.	High-strength steel	3.62	.916	Agree	3.92	.829	Agree
6.	Hybrid-electric drivetrain	3.74	.925	Agree	3.65	1.109	Agree
7.	GPS navigation	3.74	.880	Agree	3.49	.965	Agree
8.	Enclosed fenders	3.94	.819	Agree	3.60	.890	Agree
9.	Better transmissions	3.65	.987	Agree	3.75	1.135	Agree
10.	Active aerodynamics	3.85	.919	Agree	3.65	1.080	Agree
Grand Mean		3.744	.892	Agree	3.698	.952	Agree

Source: Authors (2023)

Data in Table 3 revealed that MVMW Teachers had a grand mean of 3.744 and the standard deviation range of .892. While the registered MVM Technicians had a grand mean of 3.698 and its standard deviation was .952. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the product innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on maintenance innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

Table 4: Independent Sample t-test between MVMW Teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on Maintenance Innovations to be included in MVMW Curriculum of Craft Development Center

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	P	T	Sig	Decision
MVMW Teachers	8	3.772	.843					
Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT)	35	3.724	.910	31	.05	.036	.971	Accept

Source: Authors (2023)

Table 4 is the result the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean and standard deviation responses between MVMW Teachers and Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on the maintenance innovations to be included in MVMW curriculum of craft development center. The data revealed that the mean of MVMW Teachers is 3.772 and a standard deviation .843. While for the Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT), the mean of 3.724 and a standard deviation of .910 was obtained. The calculated t value of .036 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .971 exceeded .05 (P>.05) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT)

on maintenance innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on design innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

Table 5: Independent Sample t-test between MVMW Teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on Design Innovations to be included in MVMW Curriculum of Craft Development Center

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	P	T	Sig	Decision
MVMW Teachers	8	3.715	.844					
Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT)	35	3.646	.979	31	.05	.298	.766	Accept

Source: Authors (2023)

Table 5 shows the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean and standard deviation responses between MVMW Teachers and Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on the design innovations to be included in MVMW curriculum of craft development center. The data revealed the mean of MVMW Teachers (3.715) and a standard deviation (.844) while for the Registered MVM Technicians the mean of (3.646) and a standard deviation (.979) was obtained. The calculated t value of .298 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .766 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$), the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on design innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

H0₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on product innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

Table 6: Independent Sample t-test between MVMW Teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on Design Innovations to be included in MVMW Curriculum of Craft Development Center

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	P	T	Sig	Decision
MVMW Teachers	8	3.744	.892					
Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT)	35	3.698	.952	31	.05	1.584	.115	Accept

Source: Author (2023)

Table 6 shows the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean and standard deviation responses between MVMW Teachers and Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on the product innovations to be included in MVMW curriculum of craft development center. The data revealed that mean of MVMW Teachers is (3.744) and a standard deviation (.892). While for the Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT), the mean of (3.698) and a standard deviation (.952) was obtained. The calculated t value of 1.584 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .115 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on product innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Data in Table 1 revealed that MVMW Teachers had a grand mean of 3.772 and the standard deviation range of .843. While the registered MVM Technicians had a grand mean of 3.724 and its standard deviation was .910. This indicates that the respondents agreed that maintenance innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents. Table 4 is the result the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean and standard deviation responses between MVMW Teachers and Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on the maintenance innovations to be included in MVMW curriculum of craft development center. The

data revealed that the mean of MVMW Teachers is 3.772 and a standard deviation .843. While for the Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT), the mean of 3.724 and a standard deviation of .910 was obtained. The calculated t value of .036 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .971 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on maintenance innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State. This finding is supported by Ezeama et al., (2016) whose study on the use of auto scan tools for diagnosing vehicle systems faults found that motor vehicle mechanics trainers require capacity building to use such tools for effective vehicle systems diagnosis and repairs. Furthermore, emerging vehicles comprised telecommunications equipment such as mobile phones, printers, scanners, etc. which are now used for retrieving, diagnosing, and fixing problems in modern vehicles.

Data in Table 2 revealed that MVMW Teachers had a grand mean of 3.715 and the standard deviation range of .844. While the registered MVM Technicians had a grand mean of 3.646 and its standard deviation was .979. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the design innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents. Table 5 shows the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean and standard deviation responses between MVMW Teachers and Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on the design innovations to be included in MVMW curriculum of craft development center. The data revealed the mean of MVMW Teachers (3.715) and a standard deviation (.844) while for the Registered MVM Technicians the mean of (3.646) and a standard deviation of (.979) was obtained. The calculated t value of .298 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .766 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$), the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on design innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State. This finding congruence with the findings of Okwelle and Abigo (2021) whose study indicated that modern skills are needed for efficient performance of automobile trade students of technical colleges in Rivers State.

Data in Table 3 revealed that MVMW Teachers had a grand mean of 3.744 and the standard deviation range of .892. While the registered MVM Technicians had a grand mean of 3.698 and its standard deviation was .952. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the product innovations should be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center. The closeness of the standard deviation shows the homogeneity of the respondents. Table 6 shows the result of an independent sample t-test comparing the mean and standard deviation responses between MVMW Teachers and Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on the product innovations to be included in MVMW curriculum of craft development center. The data revealed that mean of MVMW Teachers is (3.744) and a standard deviation (.892). While for the Registered Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT), the mean of (3.698) and a standard deviation of (.952) was obtained. The calculated t value of 1.584 since the significant value (2-tailed) of .115 exceeded .05 ($P > .05$) the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of MVMW teachers and Motor Vehicle Technicians (MVT) on product innovations to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft development center in Rivers State. The finding of this study is similar to that of Wahab (2015) who affirmed that practical application of skills and the technological process inherent in the production of products, services and system in order to improve the quality of life. He further suggested that, the automobile technology is very crucial and significant to any automobile technology teachers as automobile products specifications are changing rapidly stimulated by environmental and economic factors.

CONCLUSION

The essence of establishing craft centers is to produce graduates who will be enterprising in their different field of study among which is motor vehicle mechanic work (MVMW). The recent development of new vehicles technologies, brings the concept of maintenance more sophisticated. The study therefore concludes that maintenance innovation, design innovation and product innovation items as identified in table 1,2 and 3 above are appropriate to be included in motor vehicle mechanic work curriculum in government craft center in Rivers State. Everything is changing and the only option is to follow the development, to adapt to these new changes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Maintenance innovations identified in the study should be included in the curriculum of motor vehicle maintenance works in government craft centers in Rivers State.
2. Integration of design innovations in the curriculum of motor vehicle maintenance works in government craft centers in Rivers State.
3. Inclusion of product innovations in the curriculum of motor vehicle maintenance works in government craft centers in Rivers State.

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